

REVIEW CERTIFICATE

Pak J Surg Med is delighted to Certify

Dr Muhammad Hamid Ch

for carrying out a thorough critical review of manuscript titled "Cardiac symptoms in disguise; the potential effects of COVID-19 on heart tissues and the need for warning cardiologists."

Pak J Surg Med is thankful for a meticulous through peer review and it's our pleasure to have you on the peer review board.

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Ammar Anwer

Chief Editor

Pak J Surg Med

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